

DEVELOPMENT OF MOULDED PULP PROTECTIVE PACKAGING FROM ALTERNATIVE FIBERS

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Abstract: *Expanded polystyrene foam is a standard protection element for many packaging solutions which needs cushioning properties against mechanical stresses. While its protective functions are very good (lightweight good cushioning properties, easy to 3D-form with tooling) the environmental aspect of this material is questionable due to bulkiness (high space volume) and low rates of real and viable recycling infrastructure. Due to that producers have switched to fiber solutions (corrugated board inserts, fiber foams and biopolymer fiber composites) as an alternative solution. Even though this fiber-based alternative solutions are environmentally friendlier the overuse of cellulose fibers from wood sources can also be a burden on the environment. On the other hand, invasive alien plants due to their negative impact on biodiversity and other economic damage (riverbank degradation) are one of the possible solutions for producing fiber elements.*

In this paper the development of moulded fiber cushioning elements, made from locally sourced invasive fiber alien plants (Japanese knotweed and Canadian goldenrod) and processed in Slovenia is presented as a part of the protective packaging system for household appliances. The fiber morphology and processing as well the prototyping of the moulding tools have influenced the mechanical properties needed for protection simulation due to different fiber bonding and entanglement. The obtained results serve as a basis for further development and structural analysis (finite elements modelling) of stress points for building simulation software for the use of alternative fiber solutions.

Keywords: pulp moulding, invasive alien plants, protective packaging, mechanical properties, CNC

1 INTRODUCTION

Protective packaging presents materials that are created to safeguard and cushion products during shipping, storage and handling to protect them from potential physical damage. For that purpose, different types of materials (e.g., paper, plastic, metal etc.) can provide protection and present protective packaging. While the global market of protective packaging is expected to grow at 5.1% CAGR till 2030 (Bloomberg), the development of new, environmentally friendly and recyclable, protective packaging is essential. In use are already different solutions (paper fill, shredded paper, shredded corrugated board) for protecting goods that are recyclable. However, when packing heavy industrial products there is currently no alternative at scale to EPS (Styrofoam). While there is an ongoing debate about recycling rates at scale of EPS packaging between stakeholders (Ellen McArthur foundations, NGOs and EPS producers), a recent common agreement declared EPS as recyclable (Ewasa, 2023) these figures are between 30 and 40% of post-consumer waste ratio. These figures are lower than the industry average for the pulp and paper industry (recycling rate of 82.3% (4Evergreen, 2022)), and due to the tight requirements on the time schedule of the draft version of the New Packaging Waste Directive EPS recycling infrastructure and collection business models cannot currently match the fiber-based industry.

One of the challenges regarding the use of cellulose based protective packaging is the high volume and density of fibers which can further burden the EU biomass availability. In a report by Materials Economics (2021) it is estimated that with the projected rise of the use of cellulose based sources for different applications (beside the use for energy generation) EU will have a shortage of 40–70% of available biomass (around 5–6 EJ per year). The attention regarding the importance of carbon sequestration in woody species due to their long-term replenishment also shifted the focus to alternative fiber solutions.

Fiber-based cushioning and protective packaging come in different forms. Fiber foams have already been introduced to the markets (Stora Enso Papira from 2021) which are produced from sustainable managed forests (wood-based cellulose). On the other hand, moulded pulp packaging is increasing its presence on the market. Moulded pulp can be produced with injection moulding processes where most usually a natural fiber - starch or other biopolymers are used. In a review by Rabbi, Islam and Islam (2021) point out that in this production

processed the final material properties are dependent on the chemical treatment of the fiber, matrix combination, and the fabrication process itself. The so-called Pulp Injection Moulding (PIM) method, already present on the market, is based on injection moulding (similar to plastic production) and can achieve complicated 3-dimensional structural parts which are difficult to create by conventional paper packaging or other pulp mould technology.

Beside the injection moulding systems there are the more conventional production processes related to classic wet moulding where the forming and drying process is integrated in one mould (Zhang et al, 2022). During the moulding process, two main steps are involved: vacuum forming process and drying process. Specifically, a wide variety of custom-designed moulds/tools allow the pulp to form different geometries/shapes. After that, dewatering occurs, usually by vacuum sucking to remove a sufficient volume of water (35%–50%) to form a desired shape. This process is known as the forming process (Didone et al., 2017). Other variations also include a dry mould process promoted by PulpPac where wood-based fibers are air treated on a vacuum belt to form an air-laid fiber structure (200–1500 g/m²) which is coated and laminated on a tissue material before forming by heat pressing.

The moulded protection packaging was previously analysed by Hoffman (2000), who has determined the static and dynamic properties of moulded protection packaging elements, and found that the used equation shows good correlation to the results achieved for small static loads. Similar results were obtained from the earlier research of Eagleton and Marcondes (1994), whose results showed that the moulded-pulp test samples had good cushioning characteristics for low static loadings, low drop heights, and single impacts. However, the cushioning characteristics of the material were inferior to those of EPS foam at static loadings above about 5 kPa, and where higher drop heights or multiple impacts occurred. These properties were improved by using two samples with interlocking dimples (engineered elements) - where the number of the “dimple” proved to be beneficial if in larger numbers for moulded cushioning solutions. In a more recent study conducted by Alptekin A, Çallioğlu H (2023) different mixtures (eucalyptus or pine fibers (48 wt %) compound with cationic starch (48 wt %) and carboxymethyl cellulose (CMC) (4 wt %)) and processing methods (moulded pulp, extrusion and compression moulding techniques) were tested. Composite samples indicated significantly better tensile, flexural, and compressive values, at least four times, compared with the moulded pulp samples. On the other hand, the moulded pulp samples had more than 2 times better impact characteristics against composites.

For moulded packaging applications there are several research papers which tested 80/20 straw pulp/kraft pulp mixes (Curling et al. 2017), while Be Green Packaging has introduced material made of six different resources, including bulrush, wheat straw, sugar cane, and bamboo (OAS Cataloging-in-Publication Data, 2016). These materials however do not have widely available cushioning data. One of the solutions to overcome this depletion of the available biomass in the EU is to use under-utilised cellulose sources, also for packaging papers are the so-called invasive alien plants (Kavčič, Lavrič and Karlovits, 2023). Invasive alien plants are non-native in the ecosystem where their spreading can cause economic and environmental harm to the local environment. Direct economic impacts were reported in the Eschen et al. (2023) as they may profoundly change ecosystem functioning by altering species composition, physical habitat components, nutrient cycling, primary production and damages in the flood defence structures. Their quick replenishment and spreading can be made useful if appropriate utilisation can be organised, and recently alternative papers made based from invasive alien plants have been found to be appropriate materials for packaging (Vrabič and Možina, 2022; Karlovits et al., 2021).

The aim of this paper is to describe the production process of moulded protective fiber packaging of the two invasive alien plants; Japanese knotweed and Canadian goldenrod utilisation in production. As the process of producing the protective elements is wet moulding the process of the mould with the appropriate parameters is also described. As fibers from these plants are usually shorter the strengthening of the fiber structures against mechanical stresses can be done with the addition of nanocellulose solutions. In this research the samples were mixed with wood-based cellulose nanocrystals (CNC) solution in different ratios and mechanical properties of the samples were tested. These samples will be the starting point of building up appropriate finite element models for the development of open-source software for designing protective packaging elements.

2 MATERIAL AND METHODS

The experimental part consisted of several steps: designing and 3D-printing of the polymer mould, preparation of aluminium mould and counter-mould, fiber preparation, its mixing with CNC and mechanical evaluation of compression/cushioning properties.

2.1 The mould preparation – designing and 3D printing

The desired shape of the protective packaging was firstly engineered to present a truncated cone geometry, conceptualized, and designed using CAD software.

The mould has overall dimensions of approximately 50 mm in height, a base diameter of 95 mm, and a bottom diameter of 50 mm. The wall thickness was 3 mm to ensure appropriate structural rigidity and mechanical integrity. Thickness was empirically determined to be sufficient for maintaining the screen's structural integrity throughout the filtration and drying operations, without sacrificing porosity or flow-through efficiency.

According to the length of the fibers used in the study, the mould geometry features a pattern of square-shaped apertures designed to execute the filtration function. Apertures on the curved surface measure 1.2 mm in width and 0.8 mm in height. The dimensions of the apertures were selected to ensure effective dewatering while preserving the shape of the filtered cellulose fibers.

The 3D-printing process was executed using a Bambu Lab 3D-printer, which has been validated for its precision, reliability and speed in similar applications. Utilizing a 0.4 mm nozzle, process was parameterized with a layer height of 0.2 mm to ensure optimal resolution and mechanical integrity of the screen.

2. 2 Aluminium mould and counter mould for thermoforming

To provide dimensionally more stable samples, the wet pulp was blown into a heated aluminium mould and pressed with a heated counter-mould. Both, aluminium mould as well as counter-mould were prepared to fit with the 2 mm thick sample. The aluminium mould and counter mould for thermoforming were prepared by CNC mechanical processing.

2. 3 Fiber suspension preparation

Before the final recipe for paper made of invasive alien plants were made, basic morphological properties of fibers obtained from them needed to be measured in terms of length and width were measured (Table 1) and were taken into account for final paper recipe since they can affect final paper properties.

So called JK - "Japanese knotweed paper" was made of 60% of bleached commercial softwood and hardwood pulp in the ratio 50:50, refined to 25°SR prior to use. 40% of fibers obtained from Japanese knotweed were added to this mixture. In order to improve the efficiency of the papermaking process and the quality of the final paper, 10% of fillers, 1% of cationic starch and 3% of sizing agent were added.

For CG - "Canadian goldenrod paper" 55% of bleached commercial softwood and hardwood pulp in the ratio 50:50, refined to 25°SR and 45% of fibers obtained

from Canadian goldenrod were used. The amounts of filler and cationic starch stayed the same, while the amount of sizing agent was increased to 3.5%.

Both papers were disintegrated and diluted to 1% concentration, being known as blank samples, and marked as JK (Japanese knotweed paper) and CG (Canadian goldenrod paper). Sample where 10% dry mass CNC was added were marked as JK + CNC and CG + CNC.

Table 1. Basic morphological properties of the fibers obtained from invasive alien plants.

	Parameter	Japanese knotweed (JK)	Canadian goldenrod (CG)
<i>Fiber properties</i>	<i>Fiber length (mm)</i>	<i>0.775</i>	<i>0.452</i>
	<i>Fiber width (μm)</i>	<i>18.66</i>	<i>13.85</i>

For the presented research commercial CNC produced by NAVITAS d.o.o., Slovenia was used. The preparation was performed as described by Kunaver et al. (2016). The CNC particles were suspended in water solution with the concentration of 2.68%.

2. 4 Sample preparation

For the sample preparation, the 3D-printed mould which was fitted on a vacuum head was immersed into the fiber suspension and 500 ml suspension with 1% fiber concentration was sucked through the mould to form the fiber sample on the surface of the mould. After the formation, the sample was counter blown into the heated aluminium mould and manually pressed with a heated (340°C) counter-mould for 30 seconds. After this step the final drying was done by a 30-minute oven drying at 110°C with additional thermoforming every 10 minutes.

2. 5 Mechanical testing

After the 3D thermoformed moulds were dried the samples were conditioned for 24 hours at 50% relative humidity and 23°C according to the ISO 187 standard. To check the influence of the fiber and CNC mixtures mechanical compression testing was performed on the multi testing machine (ZwickRoell, Ulm, Germany) using compression plates and a 10 kN measuring head.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3. 1 Mould preparation

As mould and tools were also prototyped to achieve good formation results there were adjustments to the design and processing of the 3D printed mould. During

the mould designing it was important that the vertical dimension of apertures is synchronized with the layer height setting to maximize the aperture size accuracy. In other words, a precise alignment strategy was employed wherein each aperture begins or ends precisely where a new layer of the print starts or concludes. This alignment was meticulously calibrated to synchronize with the predefined layer height of 0.2 mm, optimizing the structural coherence and mechanical properties of the device. This ensured a uniform flow distribution and minimization of clogging risks, contributing to both the mechanical robustness and functional effectiveness of the mould. This setting was critical in preventing any deformities or inconsistencies that might compromise the filtration effectiveness. A specific attention was directed towards the mould's apertures on both the top and bottom flat surfaces. The design eliminated the conventional top and bottom layers in the 3D-print, utilizing a grid infill pattern with infill density set at 68%. It provides an optimal combination of mechanical strength and open spaces, ensuring that the cellulose fibers were efficiently formed on the surface of the mould.

To address the challenges posed by overhang structures during the 3D-printing process, particular attention was paid to the printing angle. Angles greater than 45° were avoided in overhang features to prevent print failure or the need for excessive support structures. The geometric attributes of the screen similar to a small cup or a truncated cone enable it to act as a mould, guiding the cellulose fibers into a specific form as it undergoes the separation and partially the drying phase.

Figure 1. 3D-printed mould (left) and final moulded pulp product (right).

3. 1 Mechanical testing

The dried thermoformed samples were checked to continual compression load with compression test to test the influence of CNC addition in different invasive alien plant mixtures. In Figure 2 one can see the sample before and after the performed test.

Figure 2. Sample before (left) and after (right) the compression test.

We have assessed the compression force for the first 35 mm of compression test. As can be seen in Figure 3, the force needed for compression increase in first 15 mm, the maximum force is achieved when the sample is compressed between 15 mm and 20 mm. After that distance, the force is slowly decreasing. However, after 35 mm or 40 mm the force unpredictably increase again, due to the compressed material. This effect is due to the thickening of the base of the moulded 3D elements due to settling at the base of the shape which can be seen at Figure 2 (right). The addition of CNC for both invasive plants increase the overall values for the analysed distance.

Figure 3. Compression test of protective packaging samples.

Comparing maximum forces among samples with different fibers and added CNC, the maximum forces for each sample were also determined. From Figure 4 we can observe that the highest forces during compression test were obtained with both samples that contain CNC. Maximum force for CG + CNC sample was 375 N, while JK + CNC has slightly lower values (347 N). Actually, the same maximum forces were achieved with JK and CG samples (287 N and 288 N respectively). Even though the standard deviation among samples is quite high, the average values show, that CNC has great influence on compression strength and increase the maximum force of samples regardless of used alternative fibers (JK or CG). The high surface area of CNC enables highly reactive surfaces that increase connection between fibers as well as stiffness of the sample.

Figure 4. Max compression force.

4 CONCLUSIONS

In the presented research, the possibility of using 3D-printed mould for moulded pulp protective packaging production was analysed. Based on results it can be concluded that 3D-printed mould could be a useful tool for laboratory testing and development of new biodegradable and recyclable (protective) packaging. During the development and 3D-printing of mould, different factors should be taken into consideration. To ensure adequate dewatering, especially the shape and size of apertures (which are dependent on used fibers) should be consider. Regarding forming the fibers in the developed moulds not just commercially available fibers but also alternative fibers sourced from invasive alien plant

species have a great potential for that kind of applications, which helps biodiversity to be preserved. Comparing the overall compression strength of samples and the achieved maximum force, it can be concluded, that the addition of CNC into the pulp before formation has positive impact on higher maximum compression strength and overall strength of the moulded samples. Future research will include further optimization of the fiber preparation and mixtures with the appropriate additives (CNC, starches) with the designed mould and tools to achieve maximum cushioning properties even for higher static loads (>5KPa).

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5 REFERENCES

4evergreen (2022) Recyclability: towards 2030 and beyond, Available at: <https://4evergreenforum.eu/wp-content/uploads/WS1-Mills-network-in-Europe.pdf> (Accessed 15th of June, 2023).

Alptekin, A. and Çallioğlu, H. (2023) 'Mechanical properties of starch bio-composite and molded pulp samples manufactured using pine and eucalyptus fibers', *Polymers and Polymer Composites*, 31. doi:10.1177/09673911231161983.

Bloomberg (2023) Protective Packaging Market to be Worth \$50.15 Billion by 2030: Grand View Research, Inc. Available at: <https://www.bloomberg.com/press-releases/2023-06-07/protective-packaging-market-to-be-worth-50-15-billion-by-2030-grand-view-research-inc> (Accessed: 05 September 2023).

Didone, M. et al. (2017) 'Moulded pulp manufacturing: Overview and prospects for the process technology', *Packaging Technology and Science*, 30(6), pp. 231–249. doi:10.1002/pts.2289.

Eschen, R. et al. (2023) 'An updated assessment of the direct costs of invasive non-native species to the United Kingdom', *Biological Invasions* [Preprint]. doi:10.1007/s10530-023-03107-2.

Fogt Jacobsen, L., Pedersen, S. and Thøgersen, J. (2022) 'Drivers of and barriers to consumers' plastic packaging waste avoidance and recycling – A systematic literature review', *Waste Management*, 141, pp. 63–78. doi:10.1016/j.wasman.2022.01.021.

Hoffmann, J. (2000) 'Compression and cushioning characteristics of moulded pulp packaging', *Packaging Technology and Science*, 13(5), pp. 211–220. doi:10.1002/1099-1522(200009)13:5<211::aid-pts515>3.0.co;2-0.

Karlovits, I.; Kapun, T.; Lavrič, G.; Šinkovec, A. Invasive Plants as Paper and Packaging Raw Materials. In *Invasive Plants: Ecological Impacts, Diversity and Management*, Kuhns, G.R., Ed. Nova Science Publishers: New York 2021; pp. 1-42.

Kavčič, U.; Lavrič, G.; Karlovits, I. (2023). Alternative Fiber-Based Paperboard Adhesion Evaluation with T- and Y-Peel Testing. *Appl. Sci.* 2023, 13, 9779. <https://doi.org/10.3390/app13179779>

Kunaver, M.; Anžlovar, A.; Žagar, E. (2016). The fast and effective isolation of nanocellulose from selected cellulosic feedstocks. *Carbohydr. Polym.*, 148, 251–258.

Material Economics (2021). *EU Biomass Use In A Net-Zero Economy - A Course Correction for EU Biomass*

OAS Cataloging-in-Publication Data. (2016) Sustainable alternative packaging to replace the expanded polystyrene foam containers produced within the printing and packaging industry of Trinidad and Tobago. Available at: http://www.oas.org/en/sedi/dsd/docs/ReportT&T_2016.PDF (Accessed 1 August 2023).

Rabbi, M.S., Islam, T. and Islam, G.M. (2021) 'Injection-molded natural fiber-reinforced polymer composites—a review', *International Journal of Mechanical and Materials Engineering*, 16(1). doi:10.1186/s40712-021-00139-1.

Team, eWASA (2023) Ellen MacArthur Foundation no longer classifies EPS packaging as non-recyclable, eWASA. Available at: <https://ewasa.org/ellen-macarthur-foundation-no-longer-classifies-eps-packaging-as-non-recyclable/> (Accessed: 1 August 2023).

Vrabič-Brodnjak, U. and Možina, K. (2022) 'Invasive alien plant species for use in paper and packaging materials', *Fibers*, 10(11), p. 94. doi:10.3390/fib10110094.

Zhang, Y. et al. (2022) 'Molded fiber and pulp products as green and sustainable alternatives to plastics: A mini review', *Journal of Bioresources and Bioproducts*, 7(1), pp. 14–25. doi:10.1016/j.jobab.2021.10.003.